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MICROFINANCE AS A TOOL FOR FINANCIAL INCLUSION

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ABSTRACT

The objective of 100 per cent financial inclusion can not be achieved by the Government of India unless it looks for its enforcement in each and every part of the country. The main focus is required in the rural and remote areas. One of the most significant factors which budge towards the financial inclusion of the rural and remote population is the microfinance services. In fact, microfinance is the only way through which the financial inclusion can penetrate into the rural and remote areas which expose the most under developed territory of the country. In this paper, we have mainly focused upon the achievements of the microfinance services towards financial inclusion. The role of every participant in the microfinance market has been analyzed.

KEYWORDS: Financial inclusion, Microfinance, Participant.

MICRO-FINANCE: AN INTRODUCTION

Individuals and companies need funds for many reasons such as transaction motive, precautionary motive and speculative motive. Similarly the rural and remote populations may need funds for their daily requisites, emergency requisites or for setting up micro-enterprises. For these requirements they are generally based upon two sources, viz; formal and informal sources. Formal sources here may refer to banks, co-operatives, institutions, etc which are registered whereas the informal sources may refer to the unregistered money lenders, friends, relatives, groups, etc. Major parts of the population were incapable of acquiring loans from the formal sources for their individual requirements due to the lengthy and formal processing of loans. Hence, they were mostly dependent upon the informal sources. But where the fund was needed for setting up of micro-enterprises, the informal sources were not enough sufficient. This problem was to be sort out only by the formal sources to become so liberal that acquiring a loan was to the reach of the common people. Microfinance was then recognized as a source for social development by lifting up the poor and incapable. The Micro Financial Services (Development and regulation) Act, 2007 defines microfinance as “providing financial assistance to an individual or an eligible client, either directly or through a group mechanism for:

(i) an amount, not exceeding rupees fifty thousand in aggregate per individual, for small and tiny enterprise, agriculture, allied activities (including for consumption purposes of such individual) or

(ii) an amount not exceeding rupees one lakh fifty thousand in aggregate per individual for housing purposes, or

(iii) such other amounts, for any of the purposes mentioned at items (i) and (ii) above or other purposes, as may be prescribed.”

Where, the "eligible client" means any member of a self help group or a self help group itself or any other groups formed for the purposes of providing micro finance services belonging to anyone of the following categories, namely:

- (i) farmers owning not more than two hectares of agricultural land or such area of agricultural land as may be prescribed;
- (ii) disadvantaged cultivators of agricultural land including oral lessees, tenants, share croppers;
- (iii) landless labourers and migrant labourers;
- (iv) artisans, micro entrepreneurs and persons engaged in small and tiny economic activities;
- (v) women;
- (vi) such other categories as may be prescribed.

THE CALL FOR FINANCIAL INCLUSION

Financial inclusion means that each and every citizen of the country, who is poor, underprivileged and disadvantaged, must be delivered with the financial services available in the country. The problem of financial inclusion is less in urban areas as compared to those in rural and remote areas who have no or minimum access to the financial services. According to the World Bank's India Development Policy Report (2006), 60 per cent of India's poor do not have a bank account and 87 per cent do not have any access for credit from formal sources. It was also concluded by the study of a commercial bank that more than 51 per cent of the total cultivator households had no access to the formal sources of finance. The Khan Commission, set up in 2004 by the Reserve Bank of India in order to look into the financial inclusion, recommended for making available a basic 'no frills' banking account, relaxing the KYC norms, issuing General Credit Cards to the poor and allowing the commercial banks to use the services of the NGOs, SHGs, and MFIs as intermediaries to provide financial assistance to the poor and disadvantaged people. However, microfinance evolved in India, in the early 1980s with the formation of informal Self Help Group (SHG) for providing access to financial services to the needy people who are deprived of credit facilities. In 1992, NABARD recommended the commercial banks for financing the SHGs under a pilot project. In 1999, SHG financing became a National priority sector. The main players in the microfinance sector are the NABARD, SIDBI and the RMK who have helped in achieving the financial inclusion objective of the government to a large extent. National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development, the regulator for microfinance sector, and Small Industries Development Bank of India are devoting their financial resources and time towards the development of microfinance.

THE PLAYERS IN THE MICROFINANCE SECTOR

1. NATIONAL BANK FOR AGRICULTURE AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT (NABARD)

The National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD) aims at facilitating sustained access to financial services for the unreached poor in rural areas through various microfinance innovations in a cost effective and sustainable manner. NABARD has planned to link nearly 9.2 crore households which would ensure coverage of more than 50% women through SHG Bank linkage programme by the end of 2015. The number of SHGs financed under the SHG-Bank Linkage Programme increased from 1.98 lakh in 2001-02 to 6.87 lakh in 2006-07. Various steps taken by the NABARD in this respect are Training and Capacity building of the SHGs, Micro Enterprise Development Programme (MEDP) for Skill Development, Grant Support to Partner Agencies for Promotion and Nurturing of SHGs, Pilot Project on SHG Post office Linkage Programme, Rating of Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs), Capital / Equity Support to Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs), and Revolving Fund Assistance (RFA) to MFIs.

2. SMALL INDUSTRIES DEVELOPMENT BANK OF INDIA (SIDBI)

The Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI) started its microfinance scheme in January, 1999 with a capital of Rs 100 crore and a network of about 190 capacity assessed rated MFIs/NGOs. The SIDBI has assisted in the microfinance sector by Lending to the MFIs/NGOs, Liquidity management support to the MFIs/NGOs, Providing equity capital to the MFIs/NGOs, Providing loan to MFIs/NGOs for the transformation of their structure, Micro enterprise loans to the MFIs/NGOs, and Micro Enterprises Loan Scheme- Direct Credit to micro enterprises.

3. RASHTRIYA MAHILA KOSH (RMK)

The National Credit Fund for Women or the Rashtriya Mahila Kosh (RMK) was set up in March 1993 as an independent registered society by the Department of Women & Child Development in Government of India's Ministry of Human Resource Development with an initial capital of Rs. 310,000,000 to fill the gap between what the banking sector offers and what the poor need. The Rashtriya Mahila Kosh aims at providing micro credits to the poor women who have no access to the financial services available in the country. The RMK helps in micro finance by acting as a wholesaling apex organization for channelizing funds from government and donors to retailing intermediate microfinance organizations (IMOs), developing the supply side of the micro finance market by offering institution building support to new and existing-but-inexperienced IMOs by structures of incentives, transfers of technology, training of staff and other non-financial services, and, acting as an advocate or agent for influencing development and micro-finance policy and creating a more enabling policy and legal environment for spread of micro-finance activities in India.

4. MICRO FINANCE INSTITUTIONS (MFIs)

After the above mentioned three apex bodies in micro finance sector, Micro Finance Institutions (MFIs) are the most important pillars which assist these bodies in achieving their target of social development. MFIs are the major players of the micro finance sector accounting for about 80 per

cent of the microfinance loan portfolio. The first Micro Finance Institution was established in Bangladesh as the Grameen Bank by Professor Muhammad Yunus in the late 1970s. Through Grameen Bank, he was able to provide access to very small amounts of capital with no collateral requirements. Grameen Bank provided this capital at a very low interest rate, which was almost unheard of when lending to the poor. The micro finance institutions in India have been serving the poor for the last two decades. Currently there are about 1000 NGO MFIs and 20 company MFIs in India. The State of Microcredit Summit Campaign Report, 2005 states that the number of MFIs rose from 618 with 13.5 million clients in 1997 to 3164 with 92.3 million clients in 2004. The main work of the MFIs is to provide cheap capital to the poor and disadvantaged population.

5. SELF-HELP GROUPS (SHGs)

Self Help Groups are groups of about 10 to 20 people who come forward with an aim of eradicating poverty and social development through their own contribution. They provide low interest loans to the members after a large sum have been pooled. First of all a group is formed, then all the members contribute some capital and then they are engaged into economic activities. SHGs are sometimes also referred to as 'Micro banks' which have funds either of their own or through some other contribution of associations, cooperatives, MFIs and banks. They are the direct link to the poor people and hence the micro finance sector evolves around them. They are either linked to the banks or to the MFIs.

COVERAGE OF THE MICRO FINANCE AND CONCLUSION

Micro finance has moved a more than two decade journey and serves the financial needs of about 70 per cent of the poor and disadvantaged population in India. Financial inclusion doesn't mean only to disburse credit to the poor but also to connect them to access all the financial services available in the economy. Microfinance has helped a lot in this direction. The NGOs, MFIs, Cooperatives, NBFCs and the SHGs have been regularly connecting the poor with the NABARD, SIDBI, RRBs and other commercial banks so as to make them available with as much resource as required for their social and economic upliftment. Today, there are about 60,000 retail credit outlets of the formal banking sector in the rural areas comprising 12,000 branches of district level cooperative banks, over 14,000 branches of the Regional Rural Banks (RRBs) and over 30,000 rural and semi-urban branches of commercial banks besides almost 90,000 cooperatives credit societies at the village level. On an average, there is at least one retail credit outlet for about 5,000 rural people. The retail banking services in the microfinance sector result in fulfillment of the financial inclusion objective. The SHG-Bank Linkage programme is a good example of a micro finance instrument for financial inclusion. Financing the SHGs through the Swarna Jayanti Swarojgar Yojna (SJSY) was also a new reference of the financial inclusion through micro finance sector. About Rs 1411.02 crore in 2006-07, Rs 1857.74 crore in 2007-08, Rs 2198 crore in 2009-10 was disbursed as loans to the SHGs through the SJSY scheme. Above this, about Rs 1151.56 crore and Rs 1970.15 crore was disbursed as loans to MFIs and Rs 5559.37 crore and Rs 6991.52 crore to SHGs respectively in the year 2006-07 and 2007-08. Towards home, it can be said that microfinance sector has been playing a supporting role in the achievement of the financial inclusion objective of the Union Government and is expected to move a more ahead in the appropriate manner.

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